

Paper and Thin-Layer Chromatographic Studies on the Separation of Mixtures of Isomeric mono and Diaryl Thioureas, Thiazoles & Thiazolines

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Separation of a large number of isomeric mixtures of mono and diaryl thioureas, thiazoles and thiazolines have been tried by adopting the techniques of thin-layer and paper chromatography, using as many as twenty solvent systems of various compositions. It has been observed that these mixtures are resolved into their components in almost all the solvents by T.L.C. when such resolution is impossible on paper chromatograms; thus establishing the greater advantage of T.L.C. over P.C. in the separation of mixtures of such isomeric synthetic products.

SEPARATION of isomeric mono and diaryl thioureas, isomeric thiazoles and isomeric thiazolines from one another by thin-layer chromatography using six solvent systems has been reported earlier¹. In the present communication attempts have been made to separate more number of isomeric thioureas, thiazoles, and thiazolines from one another on T.L.C. plates using a larger number of solvent systems. As many as twenty solvent systems (Table 1) using both polar and non-polar solvents have been tried with success in separating the isomeric thioureas, thiazoles and thiazolines from one another. Attempts have been made simultaneously

for separation² of the above isomeric products. During the present investigation, it has been established that T.L.C. is not only superior to P.C. as regards the time of run, as T.L.C. takes much less time than P.C. for a particular separation, but in other respects also as T.L.C. can separate effectively the isomeric products in many solvent systems where P.C. fails to achieve any such separation. This is evident from the Table of R_f values determined by both T.L.C. and P.C. as enclosed.

Experimental

The T.L.C. applicator used was an adjustable Desaga applicator Model S-II and the adsorbent used for this technique was silica Gel G for T.L.C., mixed with binding material. The well cleaned glass plates were coated with the adsorbent to a thickness of 250 μ and the developing time varied from 12-70 min. depending upon the nature of the solvent. The plates after activation were developed, by adopting the ascending technique inside air-tight glass chambers which were previously well saturated with the solvent vapours. After the development was over, the solvent was evaporated by drying the plates and spots were visualised by spraying the plates with various visualizing agents³.

For paper chromatography, Whatman No. 1 Chromatography paper was used. 5 micro-litres of the saturated solution of the substance were put on these spots carefully in such a manner that the spots were not made bigger than 5 mm in diameter. The paper was developed in rectangular chambers already saturated with the solvent for more than 48 hours and were developed by the descending technique. The developing time period varied from 7-15 hr differing from solvent to solvent. The spots were visualized by visualizing agents as noted earlier³. The R_f values got by P.C. along with those got by T.L.C. are given in the Table 2.

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	Solvent systems used both in T.L.C. and P.C.		
1.	Water : Ethylene glycol	...	90 : 10 V/V
2.	Petroleum ether (40°-60°) : Benzene	...	20 : 80 V/V
3.	Petroleum ether (40°-60°) : Ether	...	50 : 50 V/V
4.	Petroleum ether (60°-80°) : Chloroform	...	50 : 50 V/V
5.	Benzene : Dioxane : Acetic acid	...	80 : 90 : 1 V/V
6.	Benzene : Acetone	...	50 : 50 V/V
7.	Benzene : Chloroform	...	50 : 50 V/V
8.	Benzene : iso-butanol	...	60 : 40 V/V
9.	Benzene : Amyl alcohol	...	60 : 40 V/V
10.	Petroleum ether (40°-60°) : Benzene	...	50 : 50 V/V
11.	Petroleum ether (60°-80°) : Chloroform...	...	90 : 10 V/V
12.	Petroleum ether (40°-60°) : Iso propanol	...	90 : 10 V/V
13.	Petroleum ether (40°-60°) : <i>n</i> -Propanol	...	90 : 10 V/V
14.	Petroleum ether (40°-60°) : Amyl alcohol	...	90 : 10 V/V
15.	Petroleum ether (40°-60°) : Methanol	...	90 : 10 V/V
16.	Petroleum ether (40°-60°) : Acetone	...	90 : 10 V/V
17.	Water : Ethanol	...	30 : 70 V/V
18.	Benzene : Methanol	...	50 : 50 V/V
19.	Water : Ethanol	...	70 : 30 V/V
20.	Water : Ethanol	...	50 : 50 V/V

to compare the efficiency of T.L.C. with that of paper chromatography, another method of choice

TABLE 2. R_f VALUES OF ISOMERIC MONO AND SYM. DIARYL THIOUREAS, ISOMERIC THIAZOLES, AND THIAZOLES BOTH ON T.L.C. AND PAPER CHROMATOGRAM ($a =$ T.L.C., $b =$ P.C.) IN SOLVENT SYSTEMS AS NUMBERED IN TABLE 1.

Sl. No.	Names of Compounds	1		2		3		4		5		6		7		8		9		10	
		<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>																		
<i>Mono-aryl thioureas</i>																					
1.	<i>p</i> -Carboxy phenyl thiourea	.80	.85	.05	.04	.05	.02	.06	.04	.70	.23	.12	.08	.03	.01	.05	.02	.06	.03	.06	.04
2.	<i>o</i> -Carboxy phenyl thiourea	.97	.88	.21	.18	.27	.14	.29	.16	.85	.72	.83	.70	.14	.10	.73	.62	.88	.65	.23	.16
3.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl thiourea	.80	.85	-	-	-	-	-	-	.58	.76	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
4.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl thiourea	.97	.88	-	-	-	-	-	-	.48	.80	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl thiourea	-	-	.30	.42	.27	.56	.30	.60	-	-	.80	.88	.45	.66	-	-	-	-	-	-
6.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl thiourea	-	-	.08	.50	.19	.50	.10	.56	-	-	.78	.82	.05	.58	-	-	-	-	-	-
7.	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl thiourea	-	-	.07	.43	.55	.52	.49	.58	-	-	.90	.89	.33	.52	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Sym. diaryl thioureas</i>																					
8.	Sym.di(<i>m</i>)Chlorophenyl thiourea	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
9.	Sym.di(<i>p</i>)Chlorophenyl thiourea	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
10.	Sym.di(<i>o</i>)Carboxyphenyl thiourea	.95	.91	.14	.65	.16	.66	.14	.88	.81	.88	.80	.86	.43	.80	.78	.86	.81	.87	.16	.68
11.	Sym.di(<i>p</i>)Carboxyphenyl thiourea	.37	.89	.02	.26	.03	.60	.02	.85	.26	.80	.26	.80	.03	.78	.21	.58	.20	.81	.03	.36
12.	Sym.di(<i>o</i>)Nitrophenyl thiourea	-	-	-	-	.52	.89	.22	.88	.88	.94	.89	.96	-	-	.87	.95	.84	.98	.30	.82
13.	Sym.di(<i>m</i>)Nitrophenyl thiourea	-	-	-	-	.70	.88	.39	.76	.70	.91	.70	.88	-	-	.62	.85	.77	.88	.42	.86
14.	Sym.di(<i>p</i>)Nitrophenyl thiourea	-	-	-	-	.13	.80	.12	.71	.79	.95	.80	.90	-	-	.64	.83	.67	.90	.11	.78
15.	Sym.di(<i>o</i>)Tolyl thiourea	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	.48	.88	-	-	-	-	-	-
16.	Sym.di(<i>m</i>)Tolyl thiourea	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	.65	.90	-	-	-	-	-	-
17.	Sym.di(<i>p</i>)Tolyl thiourea	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	.69	.91	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Thiazoles</i>																					
18.	2(<i>o</i>)Carboxyphenyl amino-4-methyl thiazole	-	-	.81	.88	.86	.82	.88	.89	.88	.87	.90	.88	.46	.89	.91	.89	.93	.88	.83	.85
19.	2(<i>p</i>)Carboxyphenyl amino-4-methyl thiazole	-	-	.22	.87	.24	.80	.27	.86	.26	.86	.30	.87	.06	.87	.32	.88	.33	.86	.23	.87
20.	2(α)Naphthyl amino-4-methyl thiazole	-	-	.41	.85	.77	.84	.43	.87	.86	.92	.87	.91	-	-	.82	.89	-	-	.40	.84
21.	2(β)Naphthyl amino-4-methyl thiazole	-	-	.23	.88	.60	.88	.28	.85	.70	.89	.70	.90	-	-	.68	.92	-	-	.22	.79

TABLE 2—Contd.

Sl. No.	Names of Compounds	1		2		3		4		5		6		7		8		9		10	
		a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b
22.	2(o)Nitrophenyl amino-4-methyl thiazole	-	-	.21	.87	.19	.75	.18	.81	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
23.	2(m)Nitrophenyl amino-4-methyl thiazole	-	-	.75	.86	.77	.71	.71	.79	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
24.	2(p)Nitrophenyl amino-4-methyl thiazole	-	-	.81	.87	.79	.73	.76	.77	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
25.	2(o)Chlorophenyl amino-4-methyl thiazole	-	-	.25	.91	.23	.92	.24	.88	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	.83	.92	.26	.93
26.	2(m)Chlorophenyl amino-4-methyl thiazole	-	-	.71	.89	.70	.86	.73	.87	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	.91	.88	.71	.90
27.	2(p)Chlorophenyl amino-4-methyl thiazole	-	-	.75	.90	.71	.88	.79	.86	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	.98	.93	.76	.92
<i>Thiazolines</i>																					
28.	2(o)Carboxyphenyl imino-3-(o)Carboxyl phenyl-4-phenyl-Δ ⁴ -thiazoline	-	-	.18	.91	.18	.88	.20	.83	.25	.88	.26	.87	.08	.88	.28	.86	.22	.91	.15	.90
29.	2(p)Carboxyphenyl imino-3-(p)Carboxy phenyl-4-phenyl-Δ ⁴ -thiazoline	-	-	.62	.95	.64	.89	.69	.84	.88	.90	.90	.91	.38	.90	.86	.88	.87	.92	.59	.92
30.	2(α)Naphthyl imino-3-(α)Naphthyl-4-phenyl-Δ ⁴ -thiazoline	-	-	.40	.88	.76	.91	.25	.88	.60	.88	.60	.92	-	-	.86	.90	-	-	.20	.90
31.	2(β)Naphthyl imino-3-(β)Naphthyl-4-phenyl-Δ ⁴ -thiazoline	-	-	.64	.87	.58	.93	.90	.85	.82	.85	.84	.93	-	-	.62	.91	-	-	.80	.92
32.	2(p)Nitrophenyl imino-3-(p)Nitrophenyl-4-phenyl-Δ ⁴ -thiazoline	-	-	.50	.90	.40	.91	.44	.88	.88	.86	.86	.89	-	-	.82	.87	.84	.92	.26	.92
33.	2(o)Nitrophenyl imino-3-(o)Nitrophenyl-4-phenyl-Δ ⁴ -thiazoline	-	-	.69	.93	.55	.92	.67	.85	.62	.88	.60	.91	-	-	.60	.90	.61	.94	.45	.93
34.	2(o)Chlorophenyl imino-3-(o)Chlorophenyl 4-phenyl-Δ ⁴ -thiazoline	-	-	.73	.96	.70	.91	.73	.88	.68	.88	.69	.81	-	-	.61	.87	.67	.88	.60	.89
35.	2(m)Chlorophenyl imino-3-(m)Chlorophenyl 4-phenyl-Δ ⁴ -thiazoline	-	-	.88	.98	.82	.94	.93	.90	.88	.85	.80	.84	-	-	.79	.86	.81	.83	.75	.92
36.	2(p)Chlorophenyl imino-3-(p)Chlorophenyl 4-phenyl-Δ ⁴ -thiazoline	-	-	.90	.97	.89	.92	.94	.93	.86	.89	.88	.85	-	-	.85	.84	.88	.85	.78	.91
Time of development		20	8	30	8	25	10	30	8.5	20	8	12	7	15	7	35	10	30	10	30	10
		min	hr	m.	hr	m.	hr	m.	hr	m.	hr	m.	hr	m.	hr	m.	hr	m.	hr	m.	hr

TABLE 2—Contd.

Sl. No.	Names of Compounds	11		12		13		14		15		16		17		18		19		20	
		a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b
<i>Mono-aryl thioureas</i>																					
1.	<i>p</i> -Carboxy phenyl thiourea	.06	.04	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	.70	.45	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.	<i>o</i> -Carboxy phenyl thiourea	.28	.17	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	.86	.61	-	-	-	-	-	-
3.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl thiourea	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
4.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl thiourea	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl thiourea	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
6.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl thiourea	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
7.	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl thiourea	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Sym. diaryl thioureas</i>																					
8.	Sym.di(<i>m</i>)Chlorophenyl thiourea	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	.97	.88	-	-	-
9.	Sym.di(<i>p</i>)Chlorophenyl thiourea	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	.71	.86	-	-	-
10.	Sym.di(<i>o</i>)Carboxyphenyl thiourea	.15	.88	.94	.95	.91	.90	.95	.90	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	.88	.82	.91	.90	.95
11.	Sym.di(<i>p</i>)Carboxyphenyl thiourea	.02	.86	.36	.90	.35	.88	.36	.88	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	.39	.80	.35	.88	.36
12.	Sym.di(<i>o</i>)Nitrophenyl thiourea	.21	.86	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
13.	Sym.di(<i>m</i>)Nitrophenyl thiourea	.40	.78	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
14.	Sym.di(<i>p</i>)Nitrophenyl thiourea	.13	.72	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
15.	Sym.di(<i>o</i>)Tolyl thiourea	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
16.	Sym.di(<i>m</i>)Tolyl thiourea	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
17.	Sym.di(<i>p</i>)Tolyl thiourea	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Thiazoles</i>																					
18.	2(<i>o</i>)Carboxyphenyl amino-4-methyl thiazole	.25	.68	.91	.90	.91	.90	.93	.91	.92	.90	.90	.91	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
19.	2(<i>p</i>)Carboxyphenyl amino-4-methyl thiazole	.04	.70	.35	.86	.33	.88	.43	.88	.43	.88	.35	.87	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
20.	2(α)Naphthyl amino-4-methyl thiazole	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	.71	.86	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
21.	2(β)Naphthyl amino-4-methyl thiazole	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	.49	.81	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

TABLE 2—Contd.

Sl. No.	Names of Compounds	11		12		13		14		15		16		17		18		19		20	
		a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b
22.	2(o)Nitrophenyl amino-4-methyl thiazole	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
23.	2(m)Nitrophenyl amino-4-methyl thiazole	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
24.	2(p)Nitrophenyl amino-4-methyl thiazole	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
25.	2(o)Chlorophenyl amino-4-methyl thiazole	-	-	.70	.86	.72	.88	.65	.81	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
26.	2(m)Chlorophenyl amino-4-methyl thiazole	-	-	.91	.87	.92	.86	.92	.83	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
27.	2(p)Chlorophenyl amino-4-methyl thiazole	-	-	.93	.88	.96	.87	.95	.88	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Thiazolines</i>																					
28.	2(o)Carboxyphenyl imino-3-(o)Carboxyl phenyl-4-phenyl-Δ ⁴ -thiazoline	-	-	.25	.82	.22	.92	.30	.93	.26	.91	.22	.84	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
29.	2(p)Carboxyphenyl imino-3-(p)Carboxyl phenyl-4-phenyl-Δ ⁴ -thiazoline	-	-	.75	.86	.74	.91	.75	.95	.76	.93	.71	.86	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
30.	2(α)Naphthyl imino-3-(α)Naphthyl-4-phenyl-Δ ⁴ -thiazoline	-	-	.81	.88	-	-	-	-	.50	.86	.29	.87	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
31.	2(β)Naphthyl imino-3-(β)Naphthyl-4-phenyl-Δ ⁴ -thiazoline	-	-	.65	.89	-	-	-	-	.31	.88	.46	.86	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
32.	2(p)Nitrophenyl imino-3-(p)Nitrophenyl-4-phenyl-Δ ⁴ -thiazoline	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
33.	2(o)Nitrophenyl imino-3-(o)Nitrophenyl-4-phenyl-Δ ⁴ -thiazoline	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
34.	2(o)Chlorophenyl imino-3-(o)Chlorophenyl-4-phenyl-Δ ⁴ -thiazoline	-	-	.50	.91	.90	.94	.89	.92	.80	.93	.75	.87	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
35.	2(m)Chlorophenyl imino-3-(m)Chlorophenyl-4-phenyl-Δ ⁴ -thiazoline	-	-	.40	.92	.73	.90	.72	.91	.61	.91	.60	.89	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
36.	2(p)Chlorophenyl imino-3-(p)Chlorophenyl-4-phenyl-Δ ⁴ -thiazoline	-	-	.38	.91	.70	.92	.71	.93	.60	.94	.52	.90	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Time of development		20	9	20	8	20	8	25	9	25	10	25	9	50	13	35	11	30	11	70	15
		m.	hr	m.	hr	m.	hr.	m.	hr	m.	hr	m.	hr	m.	hr	m.	hr	m.	hr	m.	hr

Discussion

From the table 2, it is evident that a mixture of isomeric *p*-carboxy phenyl thiourea and *o*-carboxy phenyl thioureas and a mixture of *p*-chloro phenyl thiourea and *o*-chlorophenyl thiourea and a mixture of *o*-, *m*-, *p*-nitro phenyl thioureas were separated from one another using twelve solvent systems. But in these solvent systems, except a few, paper chromatography was not at all effective in separating isomeric products from one another, although T.L.C. exhibited its efficiency as a suitable technique for such separations. Similar observations were also made in case of isomeric sym. diaryl thioureas, isomeric thiazoles and isomeric thiazolines which were actually separated from one another as evident from their R_f values as given in the Table 2.

From these observations, it is clear that T.L.C. is not only a quicker process than P.C. as evident from Table 2 for separation of such isomeric mixtures but a more effective one also. It is possible to separate the various isomers as given in the table

from one another present in an actual mixture on a T.L.C. plate, while such is not possible on paper.

The details of the R_f values of various isomers both on T.L.C. and P.C. chromatograms are given side by side for an easy comparison in the Table 2 along with the time periods of development.

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